

SKIN DISEASE DETECTION USING CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS

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Abstract— Dermatology is the branch of bioscience that deals with treating and diagnosing skin disorders and allergies that can be caused due to various geographical and biological factors. However, human skin is a complex and unpredictable domain to define, synthesize and analyze and to rather to distinguish disorders affecting with skin. To address this issue, Researchers are still working to figure out and model human skin behaviour to automate the process of skin disease detecting through victimization that uses vision techniques to meet the criteria of medical science. Patients in remote areas where access to quality medical facilities is still limited may ignore symptoms and exacerbate their conditions. Automated medical paradigms are necessary to effectively address these issues and provide convenient and accessible solutions to people's needs. The emergence of automated paradigms for detecting skin diseases is a promising solution to ensure accurate diagnosis of skin-related issues.

A multiclass deep learning model has been proposed to develop that can differentiate between healthy skin and skin affected by a disease, and also categorize various types of skin diseases. We used Deep Learning, a type of machine learning that uses large datasets to reduce the number of classifiers required to train our model.

This approach lets the machine to learn and divide the provided data into levels of predictions and in a very short period of time gives delivers accurate results, thus our work aims to promote and support development of Dermatology. The algorithm we used here is Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) as it is one of the most preferred algorithms for image classification.

Keywords- Skin disease, CNN, deep learning, classification, diagnosis, medical imaging, data preprocessing

I. INTRODUCTION

Skin disease is a common issue faced worldwide by public and their diagnosis is normally performed through visual inspection by a dermatologist. But not all may be benefitted with these facilities like people in remote areas has limited access to medical facilities that may cause delayed diagnosis and treatment, which can potentially lead to serious health problems. Here rises the need and potential for an automated skin disease detection system that shows accurate

results and making it convenient and accessible to anyone, regardless of their location and time. In recent years, the field of medical image analysis has shown promising results with the use of deep learning techniques like Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). The Convolutional Neural Networks classifies and categorizes diseases after being processed and trained. As input, an image of a skin lesion is taken by the proposed system, which predicts the type of skin disease it represents. Using transfer learning techniques with a pre-trained CNN model, the system was trained on a large number of images of different skin diseases.

Standard evaluation metrics, such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score, were used to evaluate the system's performance. The proposed system has the potential to improve patient outcomes by assisting dermatologists in making accurate and timely diagnoses of various skin diseases, as the results demonstrate its high accuracy in prediction. In addition, where access to dermatologists is limited, the system can serve as a screening tool for early detection of skin diseases in populations.

II. CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS

The application of CNN (Convolutional Neural Network) as a deep learning algorithm is used in detecting skin diseases through processing medical images. A neural network called CNN is designed for image processing tasks and can automatically learn and identify features within images.

The CNN model in the skin disease detection system is trained on a large dataset of skin disease images to learn the patterns and features that are characteristic of different skin diseases. Several layers, including convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers, constitute the CNN model

The CNN model extracts feature from input images by applying filters to image pixels through convolutional layers during training. Then, the feature maps are down sampled by the pooling layers, which reduces the data's dimensionality and makes it easier to handle computationally. The

classification is performed by the fully connected layers using the learned features, finally.

After training the CNN model, it can be utilized to identify skin diseases in new images by feeding them into the model and acquiring a diagnosis of the skin disease. CNN offers a potent and precise means of detecting and diagnosing skin diseases.

Fig1

[Fig 1] shows the CNN architecture, comprising of several convolutional and pooling layers, followed by fully connected layers

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

A thorough research has been done with papers proposing the idea of skin disease detection using Convolutional Neural Networks and reviews based on those latest papers with the techniques used are referred and mentioned below:

Srujan S, Chirag M Shetty, Mohammed Adil, Sarang P K, Roopitha C et al. [1] (2022) in their paper titled “Skin Disease Detection using Convolutional Neural Network” presents a CNN model that is trained on dataset of skin lesion images for classifying skin diseases. The significance of early detection and diagnosis of skin diseases is discussed by the authors, along with the difficulties related to manual diagnosis.

In their study, the authors talk about the dataset they used, which comprises images of different skin diseases gathered from the internet. The preprocessing steps taken to enhance the quality of the images and prepare them for training the CNN model are explained along with their results. The proposed system's potential for improving the diagnosis of skin diseases is discussed by comparing the authors' results to those of previous studies. The paper provides a thorough review of relevant literature and outlines the creation of a skin disease detection system using CNN, ultimately leading to the conclusion

Ahmed A. Elngar et al. [2](2021), in their paper titled “Intelligent System for Skin Disease Prediction using Machine Learning” aimed in creating an accurate model to aid dermatologist in diagnosing skin diseases. Data containing clinical information and images of patients with

various skin conditions were collected. For feature extraction and classification, a CNN model was utilized in the study. Performance of the proposed system was assessed using several evaluation metrics and a comparison study using other machine learning algorithms such as support vector machines (SVM), k-nearest neighbors (KNN), and random forests (RF) was also made. In terms of accuracy and F1 score, all other algorithms were outperformed by the proposed CNN model, according to the results. The proposed intelligent system has the potential to improve the accuracy of skin disease diagnosis for dermatologists, according to the study's conclusion.

Inthiyaz, S., Altahan, B. R., Ahammad, S. H., Rajesh, V., Kalangi, R. R., Smirani, L. K., Hossain, M. A., & Rashed, A. N. Z. et al. [3] (2021) in their paper titled “Skin disease detection using deep learning” discuss the importance of detecting skin disease and the challenged overcome to get accurate results. A dataset of images featuring different skin diseases and healthy skin was gathered by the authors from publicly accessible sources. The images were preprocessed by resizing and normalizing them. Then, the CNN model was trained using a transfer learning approach with the Inception V3 architecture.

The proposed system achieved high accuracy in detecting various skin diseases, such as melanoma, psoriasis, and eczema, according to the study results. They compared their system's performance with other state-of-the-art methods and demonstrated that their method surpassed them. To conclude the authors were successful in proposing a deep learning-based method for early disease detection and achieve accuracy and it highlighted the technologies used in the field of medical science.

Leelavathy S, Jaichandran R, Shobana R, Vasudevan, Sreejith S Prasad and Nihad et al. [4] in their paper titled “Skin Disease Detection using Computer Vision and Machine Learning Technique” emphasized on improving patient outcomes and reduce healthcare costs by early detection and diagnosis of skin diseases. The use of computer vision and machine learning techniques for skin disease diagnosis is reviewed by the authors, based on existing literature. Including their ability to automatically extract relevant features and process large amounts of data, the advantages of these techniques are highlighted. In addition, the techniques have been used to study different types of skin diseases such as melanoma, psoriasis, and eczema. The paper presents a promising approach for improving skin disease diagnosis by providing a comprehensive review of the use of computer vision and machine learning techniques for skin disease detection.

Viswanatha Reddy Allugunti et al. [5] in their paper titled “A machine learning model for skin disease classification using convolution neural network” focused on developing an efficient model for skin disease classification using CNN. The study explains the various challenges and how the automated skin disease classification overcome these challenges.

Using deep learning models, especially CNNs, can automatically extract relevant features from images, improving the accuracy of skin disease classification, as highlighted by the study. Describing the process of developing the proposed CNN model, which includes data preprocessing, training, and validation, is the focus of the study. The ISIC 2017 Skin Lesion Analysis dataset, comprising skin lesion images labeled with various skin diseases, was used for the study. A subset of this dataset was used to train and validate the CNN model.

The proposed CNN model achieved high accuracy in classifying skin diseases, surpassing previous studies that used SVM and other machine learning techniques, as demonstrated by the study results. The proposed CNN model can be utilized as a dependable tool for the automated classification of skin diseases, which can aid dermatologists in diagnosis and treatment, as concluded by the study.

Kritika Sujay Rao, Pooja Suresh Yelkar, Omkar Narayan Pise, and Dr. Swapna Borde et al. [6] in their paper entitled "Skin Disease Detection using Machine Learning" discusses on various studies using different machine learning algorithms. Improving the accuracy of classification models is highlighted by the authors, who emphasize the significance of feature extraction techniques including texture analysis, color-based segmentation, and morphological operations.

In addition, the article addresses various obstacles encountered in the identification of skin diseases, including imbalanced datasets, restricted data accessibility, and the necessity of expert annotation. To tackle these challenges, the authors suggest utilizing a transfer learning technique. This involves pre-training the model on a vast collection of general skin images and then fine-tuning it on a smaller dataset of particular skin diseases.

IV. MOTIVATION

To provide a quicker and more precise way of diagnosing skin diseases, a skin disease prediction system using CNN has been developed. In areas where specialized medical care is limited or dermatologists are not readily available, this can be particularly helpful.

Using a skin disease prediction system based on CNN has the following benefits:

1. Accuracy - CNN models have demonstrated high accuracy in image classification, even with medical images. Potentially reducing the number of misdiagnoses and improving patient outcomes, the system can provide accurate diagnoses.
2. Speed - It is possible to diagnose a skin condition in a matter of seconds due to the quick and efficient processing of large amounts of data by CNN models. Faster treatment may be enabled, saving time for both patients and medical professionals.

3. Accessibility - As long as there is an internet connection, the skin disease prediction system based on CNN can be accessed from anywhere for predicting skin diseases. Expert opinions on skin conditions can be received by patients in remote or underserved areas without having to travel long distances.
4. Cost Effective - The system has the potential to lower the cost of diagnosing skin diseases by reducing the need for in-person consultations and improving the accuracy of diagnoses, which could lead to a decrease in expensive treatments.

V. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Skin disease detection using CNN was a challenging work adopted in order to create a desired result that led to a widespread change.

The following are the methodologies involved to develop this skin disease detection system using CNN

Fig 2

Fig [2] describes the data flow model of the proposed methodology

1. Data Gathering
The proposed system is being assessed on dermatoscopic image collected publicly from users. The images collected from users contain various categories irrespective of age, skin types and genders. Each image depicting a type of skin disease should be assigned a corresponding label, meaning that the dataset needs to be labeled.
2. Data Preprocessing
The collected image is preprocessed to remove noise and unwanted artifacts. Image augmentation techniques such as rotation, scaling, and cropping are applied to increase the variability of the image so that it can be processed in order to detect the disease.

3. Model architecture design:

A convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture is designed to learn features from input images for model architecture design. Several convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers make up the architecture.

4. Model Training

The preprocessed image is used to train the designed CNN architecture with backpropagation and gradient descent algorithms. The loss function, which measures the difference between the predicted and actual labels of the images, is minimized during training of the model.

5. Model Evaluation

The trained CNN model is evaluated on a separate set of images, which were not used for training. The evaluation is performed using various performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score.

6. Model Deployment

The trained and evaluated model is deployed in a web application or a mobile application for users to interact with. Users can upload an image of their skin disease to the application, and the model predicts the type of skin disease in real-time.

- *Building the Model*

The system is built using the Flask framework and a pre-trained CNN model loaded from a file. The model is trained on a large dataset of images of healthy and diseased skin to accurately classify an input image of skin into healthy or suffering from a disease.

The system accepts an image in base64 format through a POST request to the '/predict' endpoint. The image is then decoded and resized before being fed into the CNN model. The model predicts the skin disease type and returns the label as a JSON response. This system has the potential to significantly improve the accessibility and accuracy of skin disease diagnosis, and ultimately contribute to better healthcare outcomes

a) *Importing Libraries*

```
1 from flask import Flask, request, jsonify
2 import base64
3 from io import BytesIO
4 import numpy as np
5 from PIL import Image
6 import tensorflow as tf
7 from tensorflow.keras.models import load_model
```

Fig 3

- Flask: web application framework written in Python used for building applications and APIs by providing simple and flexible way for developing web applications
- request: a module that is part of Flask helping in accessing incoming data and also handles HTTP requests such as POST, GET, DELETE, PUT etc.
- jsonify: module for converting a python dictionary into a JSON response
- base64: module that provides a way to encode binary data into ASCII characters.
- BytesIO: this module creates an in-memory buffer that can be used as a file-like object.
- numpy: python library for arrays. Also has functions for working in domain of linear algebra, Fourier transform, and matrices.
- PIL: PIL stands for Python Imaging Library it works with images in Python
- tensorflow powerful open-source library for used for building, training, and deploying machine learning models.
- load_model: a function provided by the TensorFlow Keras API that allows loading a pre-trained model from a saved file. It is used to load the skin disease detection model in this code snippet.

b) *Accuracy in predicting model*

```
def top_2_accuracy(y_true, y_pred):
    return tf.keras.metrics.top_k_categorical_accuracy(y_true, y_pred, k=2)

custom_objects = {'top_2_accuracy': top_2_accuracy}

app = Flask(__name__)
```

Fig 4

The second section [Fig 4] explains about a custom metric function called top_2_accuracy using the tf.keras.metrics.top_k_categorical_accuracy function with k=2. This custom metric is used to evaluate the accuracy of the model in predicting the top 2 classes of the input.

c) *Training the model*

```
with tf.keras.utils.custom_object_scope(custom_objects):
    model = load_model('model.h5')
```

Fig 5

The third section [Fig 5] This code block loads a pre-trained Keras model stored in a file called

'model.h5'. 'load_model' function from the 'tensorflow.keras.models' module is used to load the model.

```

PROBLEMS 1 OUTPUT DEBUG CONSOLE TERMINAL
(.venv) PS C:\xampp\htdocs\ski\flask > & c:/xampp/htdocs/ski/flask/.venv/scripts/Activate.ps1
(.venv) PS C:\xampp\htdocs\ski\flask > python app.py
WARNING:tensorflow:No training configuration found in the save file, so the model was 'not' compiled. Compile it manually.
* Serving Flask app "app"
* Debug mode: on
WARNING: This is a development server. Do not use it in a production deployment. Use a production WSGI server instead.
* Running on http://127.0.0.1:5000
Press CTRL+C to quit
* Restarting with stat
WARNING:tensorflow:No training configuration found in the save file, so the model was 'not' compiled. Compile it manually.
* Debugger is active!
* Debugger PIN: 110-580-459
1/1 [=====] - 2s 2s/step
127.0.0.1 - - [02/May/2023 12:28:33] "POST /predict HTTP/1.1" 200 -
    
```

Fig 6

[Fig 6], uses the trained model to classify the disease detected from the image detected by the user. The image is preprocessed and trained using the model to obtain a predicted label. The system also displays the predicted label to users to see the result.

Fig 7

In the Figure [Fig 7], shows the interface where user uploads the image files

Fig 8

Fig [8] displays the image on uploading image

Fig 9

Fig [9] predicts the disease after uploading

VI. CONCLUSION

The research paper concluded by presenting a convolutional neural network-based machine learning model for classifying skin diseases. Using dermatology images, the proposed model achieved promising results in accurately classifying various skin diseases. Dermatologists can make accurate diagnoses with the help of the model, which has potential for clinical application. Leveraging machine learning techniques is crucial in improving the accuracy and efficiency of skin disease diagnosis, as highlighted by the study. The system proved effective and successful in detecting the diseases fulfilling user requirements.

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] S. Srujan, C. M. Shetty, M. Adil, S. P. K, and R. C. H, "Skin Disease Detection using Convolutional Neural Network," International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering, vol. 8, no. 2S9, pp. 693-697, 2022
- [2] Ahmed A. Elngar, Ayman M. Abdalla, Mohammed F. Tolba, Aboelmagd M. Noureldin, and Rami J. Luqman, "Intelligent System for Skin Disease Prediction using Machine Learning," IEEE Access, vol. 9, pp. 117658-117669, 2021. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3107405.
- [3] Inthiyaz, S., Altahan, B. R., Ahammad, S. H., Rajesh, V., Kalangi, R. R., Smirani, L. K., Hossain, M. A., & Rashed, A. N. Z. (2021). Skin disease detection using deep learning. Pattern Recognition Letters, 149, 64-71
- [4] . Leelavathy, S., Jaichandran, R., Shobana, R., Vasudevan, S., Prasad, S. S., & Nihad, A. (2020). Skin disease detection using computer vision and machine learning technique. European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine, 7(4), 2999.
- [5] Allugunti, V. R. (2022). A Machine Learning Model for Skin Disease Classification Using Convolutional Neural Network. International Journal of Clinical and Preventive Dentistry, 3(1), 141-147.
- [6] Rao, K. S., Yelkar, P. S., Pise, O. N., & Borde, S. (2020). Skin Disease Detection using Machine Learning. International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology, 9(03), 332-335.